

Mainstreaming carbon farming practices in Cyprus Oliviculture: The Carbonica Project

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Olive groves play a vital role in Mediterranean agriculture, not only as a cornerstone of local economies but also as potential carbon sinks. Sustainable soil management in these systems is key to enhancing productivity while mitigating carbon losses. The CARBONICA project is actively investigating practical, low-input carbon farming strategies suited to the semi-arid conditions of Cyprus. Among these, spontaneous cover cropping and the incorporation of pruned biomass have emerged as promising approaches due to their feasibility and positive impact on soil health. Research shows that olive pruning generates substantial biomass, often exceeding 1,300 kg per hectare annually, yet much of this carbon is lost through combustion. By shredding and reintegrating pruned material into the soil, carbon retention can be significantly improved while enhancing soil structure and nutrient availability. Similarly, managed cover crops help stabilize organic carbon, reducing erosion and improving moisture retention. However, timing and management are critical to prevent competition with olive trees, particularly in water-limited environments. At the Agricultural Research Institute's Achelia-Paphos site, experimental olive plots are testing the combined effects of pruning incorporation, cover cropping, and reduced tillage. These interventions aim to strike a balance between maximizing carbon sequestration and maintaining agronomic viability. The project employs field sensors, laboratory analysis, and remote sensing techniques to assess changes in soil organic carbon, soil structure, mineral content and soil CO₂ emissions. By validating these methods, CARBONICA seeks to bridge the gap between scientific research and on-the-ground agricultural practices, ensuring that sustainable solutions are both practical and scalable for olive farmers.

Keywords: Carbon farming, soil health, carbon sequestration, oliviculture, sustainability.

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